

**Ukrainian Conference
with International Participation**

**CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS
AND
TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE**

**29-30 May 2024
Kyiv
Ukraine**

Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry
of National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Scientific Council

“Chemistry and Technology of Surface Modification”
Interbranch Scientific and Technical Complex “Surface Chemistry”

Ukrainian Conference with International Participation
**“CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS AND
TECHNOLOGY OF SURFACE”**

Book of abstracts

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Scientific Council “Chemistry and Technology of Surface Modification”
Interbranch Scientific and Technical Complex “Surface Chemistry”

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Poster Presentation

1. Theory of Chemical Structure and Reactivity of Solid Surface

1. N.G. Kobylinska¹, V.Ya. Demchenko¹, **V.Ya. Chernii**². **Environmental applications of chemical engineered silica with immobilized mercapto-containing derivatives of succinic acid** (¹*A.V. Dumansky Institute of Colloid and Water Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*V.I. Vernadsky Institute of General and Inorganic Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
2. S. Dähne¹, K. Yesudas², **M.L. Dekhtyar**³. **An insight into the polymethine nature of Vis/NIR-chromophores** (¹*Federal Institute of Materials Research and Testing (BAM), Berlin, Germany*, ²*Inorganic & Physical Chemistry Division, CSIR Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Telangana State*, ³*Institute of Organic Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
3. **O.A. Dudarko**^{1,2}, N.G. Kobylinska³. **Acidic modified diatomite as a low-cost adsorbent for simultaneously removal of ecotoxic metals in water medium** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Department of Molecular Sciences, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Uppsala*, ³*A.V. Dumansky Institute of Colloid and Water Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
4. **I.S. Horbaniuk**, V.V. Brei. **Catalytic conversion of glucose into propylene glycol over copper based catalysts** (*Institute for Sorption and Problems of Endoecology, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
5. **V.Yu. Klevets**¹, N.D. Savchenko¹, A.G. Slivka¹, Y.I. Cheipesh², A.I. Susla¹, V.Yu. Bihanych¹, O.O. Gomonnai¹. **Energy diagram of the oxidized tin selenide surface** (¹*Uzhhorod National University, Ukraine*, ²*Instituut-Lorentz, Leiden University, The Netherlands*).
6. T.S. Hubetska, V.Ya. Demchenko, **N.G. Kobylinska**. **Synthesis and crystal chemistry of hydrotalcite-supergroup Mg,Fe-layered double hydroxide materials and their performance in the pharmaceuticals removal** (*A.V. Dumansky Institute of Colloid and Water Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
7. Yu.I. Mazna, O.V. Zuy, **N.G. Kobylinska**. **Shape formation of silver halide microstructures in the indicator systems: Effect of the halide sources and conditions of precipitation reactions** (*A.V. Dumansky Institute of Colloid and Water Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
8. **D.B. Nasiedkin**, L.F. Sharanda, Yu.V. Plyuto. **DFT simulation of interaction of graphene and silica nanoadditives with glycerol lubricant base fluid** (*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
9. **N.O. Oliinyk**, G.D. Ilnitska, G.A. Petasyuk, G.A. Bazaliy, S.D. Zabolotnyi. **Influence of pretreatment and flotation separation on the physico-chemical and morphometric characteristics of synthetic diamond powders** (*V. Bakul Institute for Superhard Materials, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
10. **L.M. Polishchuk**^{1,2}, D.A. Cauzzi². **Solid aminosilica sorbents for absorption of CO₂** (¹*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*, ²*Department of Chemistry, Life Sciences and Environmental Sustainability University of Parma, Italy*).

93. **Z.A. Matysina**¹, N.A. Gavrylyuk^{1,2}, An.D. Zolotarenko^{1,2}, Al.D. Zolotarenko^{1,2}, M.T. Kartel², Yu.I. Zhirko³, Yu.M. Solonin¹, D.V. Schur^{1,3}, M.T. Gabdullin⁴, N.Y. Akhanova⁴, M. Ualkhanova⁵, A.D. Zolotarenko¹, O.O. Havryliuk². **Multilayer film of hollow, endohedral or hydrogenated fullerenes on the surface of an atomic crystal** (¹Frantsevich Institute for Problems of Materials Science, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ³Institute of Applied Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Sumy, ⁴Kazakh-British Technical University (KBTU), Almaty, ⁵NJSC "D. Serikbayev East Kazakhstan Technical University", Oskemen).
94. **N. Mazur**, O. Kapush, O. Isaieva, V. Dzhagan, V. Yukhymchuk. **Detection of explosive materials using SERS approach** (*V.Ye. Lashkaryov Institute of Semiconductors Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
95. **R. Mazurenko**^{1,2}, S. Prokopenko¹, M. Godzierz², A. Hercog², A. Kobylukh², G. Gunja¹, S. Makhno^{1,3}, U. Szeluga², P. Gorbyk¹, B. Trzebicka². **Epoxy-based composites filled with graphene nanoplatelets modified by substituted ferrites (NiZn)_{1-x}Mn_xFe₂O₄ for absorption of electromagnetic waves of high frequency range** (¹Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²Centre of Polymer and Carbon Materials, Polish Academy of Sciences, Zabrze, ³Ningbo Sino-Ukrainian New Materials Industrial Technologies Institute, P.R. China).
96. **K.V. Michailovska**, **P.E. Shepeliavyl**, V.A. Dan'ko, O.V. Dubikovskiy, V.K. Lytvyn. **Formation of nanosilicon structures based on SiO_x films modified with samarium** (*V.Ye. Lashkaryov Institute of Semiconductor Physics, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
97. **A.I. Misiura**^{1,2}, V.O. Fisun¹, T.M. Pinchuk-Rugal¹, Ye.P. Mamunya². **Raman spectroscopy of polyamide-6/MWCNT composites** (¹Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine, ²E.O. Paton Electric Welding Institute, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv).
98. **L.V. Nosach**¹, E.M. Pakhlov¹, E. Skwarek². **Enhancing the functional properties of nanosilica through mechanosorption modification with zinc salts** (¹Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²Maria Curie-Skłodowska University, Lublin, Poland).
99. **Y.A. Onanko**¹, D.V. Charnyi¹, M.V. Yatsiuk¹, E.M. Matselyuk¹, S.V. Marysyk¹, A.P. Onanko², O.P. Dmytrenko², M.P. Kulish², T.M. Pinchuk-Rugal², A.M. Gaponov², L.I. Kurochka², P.P. Ilyin². **Anelasticity of SiO₂, nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polymers** (¹Institute of Water Problems and Land Reclamation, NAAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²Physics Department, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine).
100. **Y.A. Onanko**¹, D.V. Charnyi¹, M.V. Yatsiuk¹, E.M. Matselyuk¹, S.V. Marysyk¹, A.P. Onanko², O.P. Dmytrenko², M.P. Kulish², T.M. Pinchuk-Rugal², A.M. Gaponov², L.I. Kurochka², P.P. Ilyin². **Elasticity of SiO₂, nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polymers** (¹Institute of Water Problems and Land Reclamation, NAAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²Physics Department, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine).
101. **O.I. Oranska**, Yu.I. Gornikov. **Phase transformations into the composites of silica - acetates of calcium, nickel, copper, prepared using a gel-forming substance** (*Chuiko Institute of Surface Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv*).
102. **N.M. Permyakova**¹, T.B. Zheltonozhskaya¹, D.O. Klymchuk², V.V. Klepko¹, L.M. Grishchenko³. **Borohydride reduction of cobalt ions in hybrid matrices: kinetics and efficiency of cobalt nanoparticles formation** (¹Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ²Laboratory of Electron Microscopy, M.G. Kholodny Institute of Botany, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv, ³Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Faculty of Radiophysics, Ukraine).

Elasticity of SiO₂, nanocomposites of multiwalled carbon nanotubes and polymers

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In this study elasticity of SiO₂, radiation and structural functionalized nanocomposites of polyamide (NH(CH₂)₅CO)_n, polyethylene (C₂H₄)_n, polyvinylchloride (C₂H₃Cl)_n and multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MCNT) were researched [1].

The stereoprojection of quasilongitudinal elastic waves velocity $V_{\parallel}$ in SiO₂ (isolines in km/sec) in SiO₂ is presented in Figure. The presence of the strong interaction for nanocomposites between polymers and MCNT was confirmed.

Fig. The stereoprojection of quasilongitudinal elastic waves velocity $V_{\parallel}$ in SiO₂ (isolines in km/sec)

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1. Y. Onanko, L. Kuzmych, A. Onanko, *et al.* ECS Journal of Solid State Science and Technology **13**(4) (2024) 045001.